

**“TO-PUL” ADSORBENT’S ANTIBACTERICID CAPABILITY TO SUPPLY
CITIZEN WITH POTABLE WATER IN FIELD CONDITION****Abdulaxatov B. Sh.****Military Medical Academy of the
Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan**

Abstract. In this article, the bactericidal properties of “TO-PUL” potable water purifying adsorbent obtained on the basis of innovative technologies in providing potable water to citizen in field condition and other situations were studied. Bacteriological analyzes were carried out in accordance with current normative documents, International requirements and methods, and scientific literature.

Key words: potable water, microorganism, bacteria, adsorbent, TO-PUL, nutrient medium

Introduction: in accordance to World health organization, nowadays 80 % of diseases of digestive system resulted by directly or indirectly using dirty water. The important task of technology for cleaning water to extract potential hazardous ingredients from water. There are many ways to clean water in a purpose of prevent infectious diseases in a water cleaning facility. In example, natural purification of water and filtration by slow filtration devises, coagulation, chlorination and others. In recent years, sorption technology is actively establishing to clean water. Presenting adsorbent “TO-PUL” consist of chemical element carbon (C) and it has capabilities to extract microbiologic substances and excess chlorine from water, to improve organoleptic capability of water. Additives placed on the active surface of the adsorbent allow it to expand the scope of application, due to its porous structure easily carry out chemical bonding or physical interaction with active groups on the surface of the adsorbent.

Research objective. The purpose of the study is to develop a method of deep-water purification with a modified carbon adsorbent “TO-PUL” of water infested with bactericides and to analyze the characteristics of the process.

Materials and methods. The research object is water enriched with bacteria from the intestinal wand group (BIWG) and the added carbon adsorbent (TO-PUL).

The research work was carried out in the laboratory of the Military Medical Academy of the forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Figure 1 Adsorbent TO-PUL

A large part of the experimental data is obtained from microbiological studies using water enriched with E.Coli and water from natural sources. There was used classic methods for analyzing the sorption properties of modified materials and determining water quality indicators.

Determination of the total number of microbes.

The total number of microbes is determined according to the State standard 950-2011 and represents the number of colonies in 1sm³ water. The total number of microbes in drinking water should not exceed 100. The essence of the method is to determine the total number of mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms in potable water, which are visible at 37⁰C in 24 hours when enlarged 2 times.

Day 1. The research method was performed as follows. The water under investigation was thoroughly mixed, taken from 1.0 ml and poured into a sterilized Petri cup (90-100 mm in diameter), poured over with 6-8 ml of molten meat peptone agar (MPA) cooled to 45-46⁰C and mixed. Then the planted, material was put on a thermostat at 37⁰C for 24 hours.

Figure 2 Determination of the total number of microbes

Day 2. Planted materials were examined. According to the formula, the result is given in a colony-dressing unit of bacteria found in 1.0 ml of water. KOE/1 ml. In this study, the results were negative, the colonies in the cups did not grow.

Determination of overall and thermotolerant coliopharm bacteria by titration method.

The essence of the method is based on the separation and identification of colonies specific to BIWG by their cultural and biochemical properties, by planting and growing a certain volume of water under investigation into a liquid food Glucose peptone environment -Eickman, planting it in a lactulose-catching differential environment-ENDO.

Day 1. The water we prepared for the sample was planted in 3 vials with the Eickman environment, 100 ml in 3 test tubes and 1.0 ml in 3 test tubes. The planted material were put in a thermostat at 37°C for 24 hours.

Figure 3 Determination of overall and thermotolerant coliopharm bacteria by titration method.

Day 2. The planted environment was examined. The color of the food environment is clear and gas has not formed. The intestinal wand was not detected.

Result and discussion. Bacteriology tests of the universal disinfectant “TO-PUL”, which was presented during the examination, at a specified time interval, fully manifested the bactericide property in relation to microorganisms when examined with a number of microbes in the amount of 10^5 KOE/ml gram negative and gram positive microbes. Experimental microbiological examination of modified carbon adsorbent “TO-PUL” under static conditions in water, It has been found to have high bactericidal activity against E.Coli. The adsorbent “TO-

PUL”, obtained on the basis of innovative technologies, has the properties of eliminating various contaminants of water, which allows for economic savings, low time consumption, individual use in any conditions.

References

1. Умумий микробиология . А. В. Ганихўжаева, Ҳ.А. Назарова Тиббиёт коллежлари учун дарслик 5-нашри Тошкент “ИЛМ-ЗИЁ” 2020

2. Клушин, В. Н. Особенности доочистки сточных вод гальванических производств от дизельного топлива современными активными углями / В. Н. Клушин [и др.] // Сорбционные и хроматографические процессы. - 2014. - Т.14, №1.- С. 96-103.

3. Смирнов, А. Д. Сорбционная очистка воды / А. Д. Смирнов. - Л. : Химия, 1982. - 168 с.

4. ГОСТ Р 55874-2013 Уголь активированный. Термины и определения. - М. : Стандартинформ, 2014. - 9 с.

5. Чудновский, С. М. Оптимизация процессов управления традиционными технологиями подготовки питьевой воды / С. М. Чудновский, О. И. Лихачева, В. В. Одинцов // Евразийский союз ученых. - 2015. - № 5-3 (14). - С. 14-16.

6. Синтез, физико-химические и функциональные свойства наноструктурного композиционного сорбционного материала на основе модифицированного оксида графена 2019 год, кандидат наук Бабкин Александр Викторович

7. [Развитие научных основ синтеза сорбентов на основе цеолитов и металлооксидных систем для очистки технологических газов и жидкостей](#) 2020 год, доктор наук Гордина Наталья Евгеньевна